

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-285-IG-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	20	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	4 285
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	283.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 283.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/28/2023 11:13:23 CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:14:21 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.324	1663224	32.53	145577
2	7.319	1679950	32.86	127528
3	8.250	899915	17.60	59942
4	8.763	869474	17.01	55801

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-285-IG-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	103	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 284
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	283.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 283.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 5:17:47 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:24:34 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.359	5889	0.07	643
2	7.329	8377784	97.71	661829
3	8.220	143116	1.67	8279
4	8.737	47048	0.55	3185